

TEACHER BURNOUT DURING PANDEMIC: BASIS FOR A RESILIENCE-BASED FACULTY DEVELOPMENT PLAN

NORIEL C. NAVITA, Ph.D.¹, AIDA A. CASAS, Ed.D.²

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0314-4152>

noriel.navita@dsl.edu.ph¹, aida.casas@g.batstate-u.edu.ph²

De La Salle Lipa, Lipa City, Philippines¹

Batangas State University, Batangas City, Philippines²

ABSTRACT

The study was conducted to assess teachers' burnout level during the time of pandemic using Maslach's Burnout Inventory Scale. Using the quantitative approach, the study utilized statistical treatments such as weighted mean to describe the profile of 360 respondents and assess the burnout level in these three dimensions: Emotional Exhaustion, Depersonalization, and Reduced Personal Achievement. Moreover, t-test was used to know if there is a significant difference in the burnout level in the three dimensions when grouped according to sex. Lastly, the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to know if there is a significant difference in the burnout level in the three dimensions when grouped according to age, educational attainment, area of specialization, and number of years in teaching. Based on the results, majority of the respondents have low-level burnout in the dimension of Emotional Exhaustion, while majority of the teachers experience moderate to high level burnout in the dimensions of Depersonalization and Reduced Personal Achievement. There is no significant difference on the respondents' burnout level in the three dimensions when grouped according to sex, educational attainment, area of specialization, and number of years in teaching. However, there is a significant difference in the burnout level of teachers in the dimension of depersonalization in the age group of 20-30 and 51-60. This may be attributed to the experiences gained by older teachers as compared to the younger teachers. Upon yielding the result, a Resilience-based Faculty Development Program was crafted and hereby proposed to the schools where the respondents are affiliated with.

Keywords: Educational Management, Teacher Burnout, Quantitative Method, Philippines